

Validation of a spectrophotometric method for soil adsorption study of thiophanate-methyl

D. K. Sharma*, Aditi Gupta and Rajinder Kashyap

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University, Shimla-171 005, Himachal Pradesh, India

E-mail : dksharma_dk@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-177-2633014

Manuscript received online 04 January 2012, revised 05 February 2012, accepted 07 February 2012

Abstract : With a view to study the fate of thiophanate-methyl in soil and the extent of surface and ground water contamination, the soil-adsorption of the fungicide on four Indian soils of different soil characteristics has been studied by using a batch-equilibrium method. A spectrophotometric methodology based on the reaction of the fungicide with copper(II) acetate in aqueous DMF solution to form yellowish green solution showing maximum absorbance at 395 nm has been validated for the purpose. The leaching behaviour of the fungicide in terms of ground ubiquity score (GUS) has the value below 1.8, classifying thiophanate-methyl as non-leaching pesticide and hence it does not represent hazard to ground water contamination.

Keywords : Thiophanate-methyl, spectrophotometric method, soil adsorption study.

Introduction

Thiophanate-methyl-[1,2-bis(3-methylcarbonyl-2-thioureido)benzene], a bis-thiourea based systemic fungicide, is extensively used for the control of many fungal diseases of fruits, vegetables, and field and plantation crops¹. It is a category III acute toxicant, suspected carcinogen² and has adverse effect on thyroid, parathyroid³⁻⁵, liver, kidneys and lungs^{6,7}. It also shows cytogenic⁸ and reproductive effect⁹ on non-target organisms. The widespread use of thiophanate methyl has led to potential toxicological risk to non-target organisms and public health. Like other pesticides, the fate of thiophanate-methyl is mostly played in soil. In soil environment, it gets fractionated between soil solution phase (in free form) and soil solid phase through adsorption on clay and organic fractions^{10,11} (in bounded form). Thus it affects various processes such as bioactivity, mobility, persistence, toxicity, volatilization, and bioaccumulation because all these phenomena are operative only on the unadsorbed fractions of pesticide¹². All these processes influence the extent of surface and ground water contaminations. Therefore thorough understanding of thiophanate-methyl ad-

sorption on soil is paramount for the prediction of its movement in soils and aquifers.

In view of the above-mentioned problems, a simple, sensitive, and reliable method for the determination of this fungicide in soils needs to be developed. Of the various analytical methods, namely HPLC^{13,14}, GC-MS¹⁵, polarography¹⁶ used for the determination of thiophanate methyl, spectrophotometric methods¹⁷⁻²², find wide acceptance because of the simplicity, rapidity and sensitivity of the technique. The spectrophotometric methods commonly employed for determination of thiophanate-methyl involve its conversion by refluxing under acidic conditions to carbendazim and the later is determined by UV-Visible spectrophotometry. In another method, the determination has been done using iodine-azide reaction. The above methods besides being indirect¹⁹⁻²², are tedious and time consuming involving a number of steps requiring strict adherence to experimental conditions. In the present work a simple, rapid, sensitive and direct spectrophotometric method based upon the colour reaction of thiophanate-methyl with copper(II) acetate in dimethyl-formamide-water (3 : 7 v/v) media has been developed

and validated to study the adsorption of thiophanate-methyl on four Indian soils of different soil characteristics. The yellowish green colour which develops immediately on mixing the reagents is stable for 6 h and shows λ_{\max} at 395 nm. This method is not only free from difficulties associated with commonly employed spectrophotometric methods but possesses all the important characteristics required for its successful adaptation to the adsorption study of thiophanate-methyl in soil, being free from interference of the most of the common ions present in soil. The various adsorption parameters viz. soil-adsorption coefficient (K_d), soil organic carbon partition coefficient (K_{oc}), Gibb's free energy (ΔG°) and Groundwater Ubiquity Score (GUS) have been calculated. Thiophanate-methyl adsorption isotherm on four Indian soils of different soil characteristics have been evaluated by using Freundlich's adsorption equation which is written as

$$X = K_f C_e^{n_f} \quad (1)$$

where X is the amount of pesticide adsorbed mg kg^{-1} of the adsorbent; C_e is the equilibrium concentration in solution (mg L^{-1}); K_f and n_f are adsorption coefficients that characterize the adsorption capacity of the adsorbent. The adsorption coefficients K_f and n_f are calculated from the least square methods applied to the linear form of the Freundlich's adsorption equation,

$$\log X = \log K_f + n_f \log C_e \quad (2)$$

Other parameters for the adsorption process viz. distribution coefficient or soil-adsorption coefficient (K_d), Gibb's free energy (ΔG°), soil organic carbon partition coefficient (K_{oc}) and Groundwater Ubiquity Score (GUS) have been calculated by using eqs. (3)–(6) respectively^{23–25},

$$K_d = \frac{X}{C_e} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_d \quad (4)$$

$$K_{oc} = K_d \times \left(\frac{100}{\%OC} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{GUS} = \log t_{1/2} [4 - \log (K_{oc})] \quad (6)$$

where R = gas constant, T = absolute temperature, $t_{1/2}$ = pesticide persistence (half life), OC = organic carbon content of soil. GUS score is used for predicting of the leaching behaviour of compounds. Generally they can be classified as leacher (GUS > 2.8), transition (2.8 > GUS > 1.8) and non-leacher (GUS < 1.8)²⁶.

Results and discussion

The proposed method is based on the reaction of thiophanate-methyl with copper(II) acetate in 1 : 1 molar ratio in DMF-water (3 : 7 v/v) media to form soluble yellowish green complex showing maximum absorbance at 395 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the yellowish green complex are $1.04 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.032 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. Beer's law is obeyed up to $30.8 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of the thiophanate-methyl solution and the fungicide in the range 1–30 μg could be determined with a maximum relative standard deviation (RSD) of 1.12%. The method has also been applied to the analysis of a commercial formulation of thiophanate-methyl and the recoveries were in the range 97.8–98.6% of the nominal content with RSDs in the range 0.60–0.85% (Table 1). The results have, however, been compared with an independent method¹⁹. The formulation analysis is essential not only to ensure the quality of the formulation but also to get reliable adsorption data. To assess the validity of the proposed method in soil adsorption study, effect of various common ions on the determination of

Table 1. Assay of a commercial formulation of thiophanate-methyl containing 70% active ingredient

Amount added (μg)	Recovery (%)	
	Present method ^a	Comparison method ^b
6.72	98.2 \pm 0.74	97.5 \pm 0.85
13.44	98.5 \pm 0.60	97.2 \pm 0.90
20.16	97.8 \pm 0.85	98.1 \pm 0.76
26.88	98.6 \pm 0.48	97.8 \pm 0.72

^aValues are mean \pm standard deviation for five determinations.

^bOfficial method of analysis (1977)¹⁹.

fungicide was studied. The method was found to be free from interferences of most of common ions viz. Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , SCN^- , PO_4^{3-} , CH_3COO^- present in soil. The adsorption isotherms of thiophanate-methyl fungicide on four Indian soils of different soil characteristics (Table 2) were evaluated by Freundlich's adsorption equation and these isotherms may be classified as L-type of Gile's classification^{11,27}. L-type of isotherms represent a system where the solid surface has average affinity for the pesticide and the solvent is relatively inert i.e. there is no strong competition from solvent for adsorption sites¹¹. Freundlich's adsorption coefficients K_f and n_f were cal-

Table 2. Characteristics of the different Indian soils used in the adsorption study of thiophanate-methyl

Soil sample	pH	Clay (%)	Organic carbon (%)	Cation Exchange Capacity (meq/100 g)
I	7.2	32.6	0.8	13.1
II	7.6	18.2	0.9	12.9
III	6.5	20.0	1.5	11.0
IV	6.8	23.4	1.6	12.8

culated from the plot of $\log X$ versus $\log C_e$ (Fig. 1) and results are presented in Table 3. The adsorption coefficient K_f represents the amount of pesticide adsorbed at an equilibrium concentration of 1 mg L^{-1} and n_f represents the variation in adsorption with varying concentration of pesticide¹². The observed value of n_f was less than 1 in all four cases, indicating that with an increase in the concentration of pesticide, the percentage adsorption of the

pesticide by the soil decreased. This might be due to the fact that at higher concentration, there is an increased difficulty to access the adsorption site²⁸. Other parameters such as the soil-adsorption coefficient (K_d), soil organic carbon partition coefficient (K_{oc}), Gibb's free energy for adsorption process (ΔG^0), and Groundwater Ubiquity Score (GUS) for the adsorption of thiophanate-methyl were calculated and are presented in Table 3. The value of K_d represents the extent of adsorption and in general higher the K_d value, the greater is the pesticide adsorption¹². Hence, thiophanate-methyl is adsorbed maximally in the case of soil IV (Table 3). The K_d for a pesticide is soil-specific and vary with soil texture and its organic matter content but the soil organic carbon partition coefficient (K_{oc}) is less soil specific²⁹ and is calculated by normalizing adsorption coefficient (K_d) with the organic carbon (OC) content of the soil. The value of $\log K_{oc}$ was observed 2.42 to 2.58 in all four cases which are

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log X$ versus $\log C_e$ for the evaluation of Freundlich's adsorption coefficients K_f and n_f .

Table 3. Adsorption parameters for the adsorption of thiophanate-methyl fungicide on four Indian soils

Soil	K_f	n_f	K_d	K_{oc}	ΔG^0	GUS
I	14.07	0.58	3.08	386	-2.794	0.88
II	13.96	0.59	3.26	362	-2.929	0.89
III	16.41	0.60	4.07	271	-3.477	0.97
IV	16.40	0.61	4.24	264	-3.578	0.98

closer to the literature reported value³⁰. The adsorption of pesticide on soil depends on its characteristics and is affected by various parameters. The organic matter content of soils affects the adsorption of pesticide : higher the organic matter contents, higher the adsorption³¹, which has been observed in soils III and IV. The cation exchange capacity (CEC) is another parameter that influ-

ences the adsorption of pesticide. The value of CEC is directly proportional to hydrophobic nature of adsorbent, i.e. greater the value of CEC of soil, its surface will be more hydrophobic. The most of the organic pesticides being more hydrophobic (low water solubility) thus have higher adsorption affinity for the soils with higher CEC³². The pH of the soil also governs the adsorption of pesticides. In general the adsorption of pesticides is less in alkaline than in acidic soils³³. However, at quite higher and lower pH of the soil, the adsorption of pesticides decreases due to change in the clay mineralogy or destroying of the crystal lattice³⁴. Higher adsorption of thiophanate-methyl in soils III and IV (Table 3) is in conformity with the above observations. Similar results have also been reported in the adsorption study of a related carbendazim fungicide³⁵. Thiophanate-methyl persists longer in acidic soils than in similar soils of alkaline pH where it undergoes decomposition³⁶ further substantiate the observed adsorption behaviour. The value of Gibb's free energy (ΔG°) for the adsorption of thiophanate-methyl was observed negative, suggesting the energetically favorable adsorption process. A number of models are available to evaluate the leaching potential of pesticide vis-à-vis-associated environmental pollution risk. Ground-water Ubiquity Score (GUS) is the most commonly used model which relates pesticide persistence (half life) and adsorption in soil (K_{oc}). The leaching potential of fungicide in terms of GUS index was determined by using experimentally observed K_{oc} value for each soil sample and literature reported half life³⁰ of thiophanate-methyl. The GUS (ranging from 0.88–0.98) for thiophanate methyl has been observed below 1.8, which classifies it as a non-leacher pesticide. Therefore, the use of thiophanate-methyl fungicide does not represent the real hazard to ground water contamination.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Spectronic 20D⁺ spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched glass cells.

N,N-Dimethylformamide (Merck) was purified by storing it over anhydrous sodium carbonate (AR) for two days. The solvent was decanted off and distilled, and fraction distilling at 148.5–149.5 °C was collected. Thiophanate-methyl, a standard of high purity (99.7%,

Sigma-Aldrich Loaborchemikalien GmbH) was used. Copper(II) acetate monohydrate (CDH, AR) ($\approx 0.005 M$) solution was prepared by dissolving 0.1 g of copper(II) acetate in 100 mL distilled water. The soils used in the adsorption study were collected from Solan District of Himachal Pradesh, India.

Preparation of calibration curve for pure compound :

Aliquots (0.01–2.0 mL) of standard solution ($10^{-3} M$) of pure thiophanate-methyl in DMF were diluted to 3 mL with the same solvent, mixed with 1 mL copper(II) acetate ($\approx 0.005 M$) and final volume made to 10 mL with distilled water. The absorbance of each solution was measured at 395 nm against a reagent blank, and a calibration curve was prepared. The relationship between concentration of thiophanate-methyl and absorbance was linear up to 30.8 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

Formulation analysis :

A sample (12 mg) of the formulation (Hexatop, 70% WP) equivalent to 8.4 mg active ingredient was dissolved in 10 mL DMF and filtered. The residue was washed four times with DMF. The filtrate and washings were diluted to known volume (25 mL) with the same solvent. Suitable aliquots (0.2–0.8 mL) of this solution were taken and processed for analysis as described above for the pure compound. Assay results are given in Table 1.

Soil adsorption study :

Thiophanate-methyl adsorption isotherms on four Indian soils were obtained by the batch equilibration technique using 50 mL conical flask³⁷. Triplicate soil samples (2 g) were equilibrated with aqueous thiophanate-methyl solutions in the concentration range from 34.24–102.72 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ by shaking in Incubator Shaker PT-422 at room temperature (25 ± 1 °C) for 12 h equilibrium time. After equilibration, the suspensions were centrifuged and were extracted three times with chloroform, each time using 5 ml chloroform. The combined extract was heated over a water bath nearly to dryness. The residue was dissolved in 3 ml of DMF and was processed for analysis as described above for the pure compound.

Conclusion :

The proposed spectrophotometric method for soil adsorption study of thiophanate methyl is simple, rapid and is free from interferences of most of the common ions present in the soil. The pesticide leaching is an important

process with respect to contamination risk to aquatic environment. The leaching behaviour of the fungicide in terms of Ground Ubiquity Score (GUS) was below 1.8, classifying thiophanate-methyl as non-leaching pesticide and hence it does not represent hazard to ground water contamination.

References

1. Y. L. Nene and P. N. Thapliyal, "Fungicides in Plant Disease Control", 2nd ed., Oxford and IBH Pub. Co., New Delhi, India, 1979, 248.
2. Q. Saquib, A. A. Al-Khedhairi, S. Al-Arifi, A. Dhawan and J. Mussart, *Toxicol. In Vitro*, 2009, **23**, 848.
3. A. Capaldo, F. Gay, M. De Falco, F. Virgilio, S. Valianati, V. Laforgia and L. Varano, *Comp. Biochem. Physiol., Part C*, 2006, **143**, 86.
4. M. R. Gawande, N. Murli, A. Binjhade and V. K. Shrivastava, *Int. J. Bio. Technol.* 2010, **1**, 38.
5. R. Sciarriello, M. De Falco, F. Virgilio, V. Laforgio, A. Capaldo, F. Gay, S. Valianati and L. Varano, *Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*, 2008, **55**, 254.
6. T. J. Singh, B. D. Garg and P. C. Verma, *Indian J. Pharmacol.*, 1987, **19**, 159.
7. S. Buono, L. Cristiano, B. D. Angelo, A. Cimini and R. Putti, *Comp. Biochem. Physiol., Part C*, 2007, **145**, 306.
8. R. Barale, C. Scapoli, C. Meli, D. Casini, M. Minunmi, A. Marrazzini and I. Barraï, *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology* 1993, **300**, 15.
9. Y. L. Xi and H. Y. Hu, *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*, 2003, **71**, 722.
10. R. D. Wauchope, S. Yeh, J. B. H. J. Linders, R. Kloskowski, K. Tanaka, B. Rubin, A. Katayama, W. Kordel, Z. Gerstl, M. Lane and J. B. Unsworth, *Pest. Manage. Sci.*, 2002, **58**, 419.
11. R. Calvet, *Environ. Health Prospect.*, 1989, **83**, 145.
12. M. Jaya, S. B. Singh, G. Kulshrestha and S. Arya, *Pest. Res. J.*, 2009, **21**, 101.
13. C. Ye, Q. Zhou and X. Wand, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 2008, **88**, 461.
14. S. B. Singh, G. D. Foster and S. U. Khan, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2007, **1148**, 152.
15. M. Nakamura, Y. Furumi, F. Watanabe, K. Nizukoshi, M. Taniguchi and S. Nemoto, *Shokuhin Eiseigakai Zasshi*, 2011, **52**, 148.
16. B. C. Verma, C. Chauhan, L. Thakur and D. K. Sharma, *Pest. Res. J.*, 2004, **16**, 90.
17. B. C. Verma, S. Sood, C. Chauhan and D. K. Sharma, *J. AOAC Int.*, 2004, **87**, 811.
18. M. Skowron and W. Ciesielski, *Chem. Anal. (Warsaw)*, 2008, **53**, 133.
19. V. L. Miller, E. Csonka and C. J. Gould, *J. AOAC Int.*, 1977, **60**, 1154.
20. P. K. Naidu, T. Niranjana and V. S. N. Naidu, *Int. J. Chem. Tech. Res.*, 2011, **3**, 1728.
21. S. Mandal, S. Das and A. Bhattacharyya, *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*, 2010, **84**, 592.
22. Q. Li and W. X. Li, *Deciduous Fruits*, 2007, **3**, 47.
23. C. Vischetti, C. Marcuchini, L. Leita, P. Cantone, F. Danuso and R. Giovanardi, *Eur. J. Agron.*, 2002, **16**, 231.
24. E. Papa, S. Castiglioni, P. Gramatica, V. Nikolaenko, O. Kayumov and D. Calamari, *Water Res.*, 2004, **38**, 3485.
25. D. Bhardwaj, Sharma and R. Tomar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2007, **46**, 1796.
26. D. I. Gustafson, *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 1989, **8**, 339.
27. P. Somasundaram and D. Wang, In : "Solution Chemistry : Minerals and Reagents", ed. B. A. Wills, Elsevier, The Netherland, 2006, 73.
28. K. L. Nemeth, G. Fuleky, G. Maroyan and P. Csokan, *Chemosphere*, 2002, **48**, 545.
29. J. P. Chen, S. O. Pehkonen and C. C. Lau, *Colloids Surf. (A)*, 2004, **240**, 55.
30. PVRD, Pest Manage. Regulatory Agency, Health Canada, 2011
31. S. M. U. Iraqi and E. Iraqi, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2000, **224**, 155.
32. O. R. Pal and A. K. Vanjara, *Sep. Purif. Technol.*, 2001, **24**, 167.
33. C. A. Edwards, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1975, **42**, 39.
34. M. Kumar and L. Philip, *Chemosphere*, 2006, **62**, 1064.
35. X. Li, Q. Zhou, S. Wei, W. Ren and X. Sun, *Geoderma*, 2011, **160**, 347.
36. J. R. Fleeker, H. M. Lacy, I. R. Schultz and E. C. Houkom, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1974, **22**, 593.
37. R. Celis, G. Facenda, M. C. Hermosin and J. Cornejo, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 2005, **85**, 1153.

